

King's Digital Lab
REF 2029
Checklist for Digital Outputs
Assessment

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Checklist for Digital Outputs Assessment - REF 2029

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The purpose of this document is to provide a guiding checklist for colleagues across the Faculty of Arts and Humanities who are in the process of assessing whether to submit digital research outputs to REF 2029. Its pragmatic scope is to provide a checklist that would support holistic reviews of digital outputs beyond strictly field-specific academic criteria and enhance the submitted products.

Evidence from REF 2014 analysis suggests that digital research resources “were given equal recognition to other forms of research output and that research datasets may be identified as notably worthy of recognition” (Tanner 2015).¹

More recently, cross-disciplinary research communities have pushed for the recognition of non-traditional research outputs including software (see in particular <https://hidden-ref.org/the-5-percent-manifesto/>).

Digital artefacts which could be submitted to the last REF (*Guidance on revisions to REF 2021*, Annex K: 110-112) encompass a broad spectrum and were not limited to specific types of digital outputs; however, as any 4* and 3* research outputs, they were expected to be respectively world-leading or internationally excellent in terms of originality, significance and rigour. The output must also meet the REF definition of research (*Guidance on revisions to REF 2021*, Annex C: 90). Although new guidelines are not available yet, the Research England *Research Excellence Framework 2028: Initial decisions and issues for further consultation* document confirms that ‘a very wide range of output types’ is welcome and includes software and datasets, among others, pointing to the 2021 documentation for reference (REF 2028).

This checklist builds heavily on version 1 drafted for REF2021 and continues to focus mainly on website content and research databases but includes considerations applicable to other types of digital artefacts such as datasets, software modules and data papers.

Digital artefacts which include personal or sensitive data are not considered in this checklist. The assumption is, however, that any digital output submitted to REF has been subjected to relevant ethical clearance for the institution submitting it.

It is important to remember that the content and technical structure of a digital output are interdependent; this checklist focuses on research software engineering best practices with the understanding that any review of digital outputs ought to be combined and integrated with the REF academic assessment criteria.

In addition to the preliminary checklist presented here, every research output should be assessed against specific criteria depending on its context, discipline, type and format (e.g. criteria to assess significance, originality and rigour should be tailored and vary for a digital monograph as opposed to a prosopographical database, a dynamic notebook, a virtual exhibition or an annotated georeferenced map).

CHECK-LIST

<input type="checkbox"/> Credits	<i>Are the people who produced the digital output credited appropriately on the website/resource? Are institutional logos and/or funding credentials present?</i>
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¹ Note that digital outputs can feature in a REF submission as research outputs on their own, as research underpinning impact case studies or material supporting impact case study or the narrative of environmental statements. With respect to impact case studies in the REF 2014 submission: “Many arts and humanities departments (whatever the discipline) offered evidence of impact using their digital outputs or digital engagement as part of the mix of evidence offered. At King’s, digital humanities collaborations underpinned a large number of impact case studies in a diverse range of subjects and they all seem to have done extremely well in the context of the REF mode of measurement” (Tanner 2015).

This is particularly important for REF as it relates to work attribution and to the roles different people had in conceiving and building the digital output. A statement of authorship should relate to content but also, for example, data model, information architecture, interface design etc.

It is crucial to match the output to the submitting researchers and institutions: “A digital resource should not be viewed as the creation of, for example, a single lead applicant or project director, but as a collaborative exercise to which all members of a team have made unique contributions.” (AHRC and ICT Strategy project, 2006: 26)

Example of institutional policy:

<https://www.kcl.ac.uk/policyhub/fair-publication-policy> (note that in addition to this, King’s College London recommends the use of the CRediT taxonomy (<https://credit.niso.org/>) when writing authorship and contributor statements, as good practice for publishing research outputs.)

Example of credit page:

<https://pleiades.stoa.org/credits>

□ Licences, Ownership and Copyright

Does the digital output or its submission clearly state who owns the data or the resources (e.g. images used on the site or digital archive, texts produced as part of a digital edition or used to train a model)? Does it contain copyright statements and information about licences (e.g. for data re-use)?

With respect to REF submissions, not only is ownership of digital outputs essential but their alignment with principles of research integrity, open science and reproducibility (e.g. availability of the data supporting the findings in research) as well as their potential for reuse² (e.g. availability of data for sharing with other users or justified restrictions) is also crucial. If research data are produced as part of UKRI funding, compliance with Research Council common principles on data policy should be followed.³

Choices of licences (e.g. Creative Commons) with respect to content, software and data in a digital output should be explicit and justified. Enabling data discoverability and alignment with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles (Hagstrom, 2014) are increasingly becoming requirements for digital outputs in research across disciplines and domains. Inevitably, however, contexts and disciplines define what level of reproducibility and re-use is appropriate and to what aspects of the research. For example, for a specific output, such as linguistic analysis, it might be crucial to have access to the research data or the corpus the argument is based on, while for other types of output, such as an exhibition in practice-as-research domains, documentation on the research process might be more important than providing access to ephemeral

² See Beagrie (2019).

³ See relevant UKRI guidance [Publishing your research findings](#) (2024).

With respect to data management and data deposits, see the King’s College London Library guidelines on research data management: <https://www.kcl.ac.uk/researchsupport/managing>

data.⁴

Data outputs can be complemented by data papers with associated details on licenses, ownership and copyright – this is an emergent genre that has also increased in popularity in the arts and humanities.

Example of data paper:

<https://doi.org/10.5334/johd.195>

<p><input type="checkbox"/> Editorial Context and Documentation</p>	<p><i>Does the digital output contain information about its editorial context?</i></p> <p>This is particularly important for REF as it provides a description and essential information on the digital output’s scope, limitations, date of public release and intended audiences, in order to assess its alignment to scholarly and research software engineering practices. Editorial introductions or equivalent sections of the output or submission should illustrate how the design of the digital output was consciously positioned within its wider intellectual context of relevance.</p> <p>Panel members should be able to assess the reasons why the digital output qualifies as a 3* or 4* output from its editorial context. This should be used to clarify and document the content of the output and the decisions made in all key steps of its creation, including, for example, what thesauri or controlled vocabularies are used in searching, the scholarly standards applied in the selection of material to digitise, the digitisation workflow (e.g. quality assurance of reproductions and subsequent handling or manipulation of the material in the case of a digital edition or digital archive project), transcription policy and editorial rules, when relevant.</p> <p>Editorial context and documentation should not be limited to the academic editorial practices but be complemented by and ideally integrated with information on technical development, (e.g. in the form of a technical overview describing technical infrastructure including software created or used, development approach, community technical standards adopted for the creation of the digital output, access to datasets including texts and archival records). The choice of technologies as well as modifications of community standards implemented within the output should be commented on and documented if undocumented elsewhere.⁵</p> <p>Contextual information should also include anything else that would be appropriate for any other type of research output to support its 3* or 4* assessment, including reviews (still rare for digital outputs, unfortunately), conference presentations and derivative publications.</p> <p>At a minimum, the editorial context of the digital output should include</p>
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⁴ While in the Arts & Humanities researchers do not necessarily recognise a division between the output and supporting data, “REF is moving towards a more flexible view of what the output is, so that for a practice researcher the whole lifecycle of research can be captured and the process seen as equally important as the outcome” (Beagrie 2019, 31).

⁵ See Rockwell (2012): “annotation and interpretation take place in the sphere of digital scholarship in ways that are different from the print world where interpretation often takes the form of an article or further book. Evaluators should ask about the depth of annotation and the logic of such apparatus”.

	<p>information on “its scope, its creators, its methodology, its development and future maintenance” (AHRC and ICT Strategy project, 2006: 20).</p> <p>This information should be up to date prior to REF submission (e.g. systematic check of broken links; correct tense to avoid out of date information e.g. ‘this project will...’) and packaged for the submission if the digital output is <i>in fieri</i> (evolving) or updated regularly (e.g. as a first edition or numbered version or release).</p> <p>If the editorial context on the website itself does not provide sufficient information to assess why the digital output constitutes a 3* or 4* output for the submitted researcher, the additional statement accompanying the submission should explain this (see also ‘added value’).⁶</p> <p>Examples of technical overviews: https://radicaltranslations.org/about/tech-overview/ https://ncse.ac.uk/cms/about/technical-overview/ https://janeausten.ac.uk/edition/technical.html</p>
<p>□ Edition Version</p>	<p><i>If the site is dynamic and forthcoming updates are foreseen, is there a way to retrieve the edition submitted to REF during the assessment period?</i></p> <p>Best practices implemented by King’s College London, Department of Digital Humanities and other institutions in 2014 and 2021 included the creation of site ‘clones’ especially packaged for REF submission and including contextual information targeted to that scope. For each submitted site, frozen copies acting as a snapshot for that site were created, made accessible via a new URL, and kept live for a year for the REF panel to examine. Whether hosted by KDL or another organisation, it takes time and effort to create such copies so this work should be planned well in advance for the REF submission and in consultation with faculty and the team responsible for creating these clones.</p> <p>The collection formats required for the different output types are detailed in Annex K of the REF <i>Guidance on submissions</i> (2021: 102-113).</p>
<p>□ Added Value</p>	<p><i>What is the added value of the digital output with respect to existing and comparable tools or resources? How has the potential of the medium been exploited? How innovative and/or significant is the resource?</i></p> <p><i>Does it stand in scholarly and/or digital isolation? What has been taken from earlier works (e.g. printed editions); what is new? Are there features in this</i></p>

⁶ See the REF *Guidance on submissions to REF 2021* (2021, 113) on supplementing material: “For non-text outputs, practice-based outputs or any other output where the research dimensions are not evident within the output/representation of the output itself: a written description of the research process and/or content should be provided. Wherever possible this should be submitted in REF2 in the ‘additional information’ field (maximum 300 words). Only where necessary to enable the panel to assess the research dimensions of the output, a fuller written description of the research process and/or content should be provided instead of the written description in REF2. The fuller written description should be included as part of an uploaded PDF, or on paper together with a physical output.” Panel D recommend the submission of a 300 words additional statement for most digital artefact output types, please see Annex C of the *Panel criteria and working methods* (REF 2021).

digital output that comparable tools or resources lack? Are there examples of searches to showcase research possibilities enabled by the digital output? What is the 'added value' of digital over print delivery in the context of the resource under discussion?

If not spelled out in the editorial context, this information should be provided with the statement accompanying the submission (which is up to 300 words).

The Modern Language Association (MLA 2012) offers some useful pointers to outline the innovative (or disruptive) aspect of digital outputs for those cases where this is appropriate:

- “describe how the digital output “may blend, redefine, or render obsolete the traditional boundaries between teaching, research, and service”
- “describe the process underlying creation of work in digital media (e.g., the creation of infrastructure as well as content) and their particular contributions”
- “describe how work in digital media requires new collaborative relationships with clients, publics, other departments, colleagues, and students”

□ Accessibility *Does the resource comply with digital accessibility standards (e.g. WCAG), and how effectively does it cater to users with diverse needs, including those using assistive technologies? Does the resource publicly state to the users the accessibility standard it meets, and which parts will be challenging or inaccessible to some users in an accessibility statement?*

Ensuring digital accessibility is essential for creating inclusive resources that serve all users, including those with disabilities. By adhering to accessibility standards and maintaining accessibility practices, *researchers* fulfil legal and ethical obligations while enhancing the overall user experience (e.g. can the website be navigated using a keyboard? Does it contain inaccessible PDF forms that cannot be read out on screen readers? Is the colour contrast poor so that it makes the text difficult to read especially for visually impaired people?).

Below are links to key resources on WCAG guidelines, and best practices for assessing and maintaining digital accessibility. The responsibility of making content accessible falls on editors of and contributors to the content of the site. The REF guidance states that the submitting HEI should ensure that any digital material is accessible from a range of devices (REF, *Panel criteria and working methods*, 2021:92).

Resources:

<https://www.w3.org/WAI/fundamentals/>

<https://www.w3.org/WAI/standards-guidelines/>

<https://www.gov.uk/guidance/guidance-and-tools-for-digital-accessibility>

<https://emckclac.sharepoint.com/sites/DI/SitePages/Digital-Accessibility-Toolkit.aspx?web=1> (can be viewed only by King's College London staff)

□ User experience *Does the digital resource guide users intuitively through tasks or information, and what feedback mechanisms are in place to support a seamless and satisfying experience?*

A well-designed digital resource should not only be functional but also intuitive, guiding users effortlessly through tasks or information without confusion. By prioritising user experience, the resource becomes more approachable and satisfying, reducing frustration, promoting continued engagement, and help users achieve their goals they set out to do. Feedback mechanisms, such as visual cues or confirmations, help users feel confident in their interactions and reduce errors, ultimately supporting a seamless, user-centered design that anticipates and meets user needs.

Design assessment relates mainly to how well the resource is structured to enable user navigation (e.g. browsing) and interactivity with the components of a site or external elements as appropriate (e.g. easy to use search; stated and limited dependencies on external software; clear relationships with other related online resources; performance).

For example, at a very minimal level, if entries in an index or glossary do not lead to corresponding records in a database or textual occurrences, the user experience is poor.

Interaction happens at different levels and it also involves users consuming content by reading text (or listening to text with assistive technologies, e.g. screen readers) and browsing media content. The choice of language should be appropriate for the targeted audience and consider the diversity of contexts in which content is digested. For example, providing closed captioning for videos, transcriptions for audio files, alternative formats for data visualisations and maps, are mechanisms to allow users to choose a way of interacting with the content suited to their current situation.

Example:

<https://ongtiffany.github.io/project/mmc.html>

Resources:

<https://www.designkit.org/methods.html>

<https://www.nngroup.com/>

□ Citability

Is there information on how to cite the digital output and its sections (e.g. specific records)? Are persistent identifiers provided at the level of relevant site components? Are Digital Objects Identifiers (DOIs) provided for datasets or other relevant records?

Are search results saveable or is it possible to download search data or other data?

If it is a hybrid publication (print and digital), is it clear how they relate with respect to citation conventions?

Example of citation recommendations:

<https://finerollshenry3.org.uk/content/book/citations.html>

<https://www.software.ac.uk/publication/how-cite-and-describe-software>

Example of citation format provided at record level:

<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISico00612>

[https://ncse.ac.uk/periodicals/mruc/issues/vm2-](https://ncse.ac.uk/periodicals/mruc/issues/vm2-ncseproduct1720/page/1/articles/aroo100/)

[ncseproduct1720/page/1/articles/aroo100/](https://ncse.ac.uk/periodicals/mruc/issues/vm2-ncseproduct1720/page/1/articles/aroo100/)

□ **Visual Form** *Does the output visually reflect the project's content and purpose, and align with the target audience's expectations with consistent approach?*

A well-crafted visual output is crucial for communicating the output's content and purpose, ensuring it resonates with the target audience while guiding them intuitively through the experience. Effective design goes beyond aesthetics - it must align with user expectations and research content, fostering trust and engagement. Leveraging design heuristics, such as consistency and simplicity, helps to create a cohesive visual language and system, where visual elements like colours, typography, and imagery work together to reinforce the output goals and enhances usability. Other elements of the user interface might be relevant for its assessment as 3* or 4* output e.g. whether it is overly complex or appropriately designed for its intended audiences or whether, if applicable, images are of sufficient quality to investigate research claims on the material.

The visual form should be responsive and adaptable, ensuring it supports the fruition of the research content and user experience across different platforms and devices. The visual form should support, not overshadow the content or distract users, but serving as a seamless extension of the output's main purpose.

Example:

<https://ongtiffany.github.io/project/maoeraobjects.html>

<https://ongtiffany.github.io/project/renaissanceskin.html>

Resources:

<https://www.nngroup.com>

<https://www.medium.com>

<https://www.uxdesigninstitute.com/blog>

<https://dribbble.com/>

□ **Dynamic components** *If the site allows for external users to import or manipulate data (e.g. lemmatise textual corpora) and analyse them dynamically (e.g. applying scripts or algorithms and create visualisations), is there any documentation on the data workflow to assess the quality of the software and of the process of generating and interpreting results?*

Some digital outputs are enhanced by the provision of technical interfaces like OAI-PMH, REST, APIs etc., which allow the reuse of the data in other contexts. Documentation on the data structures and schemas, for example, is essential to assess these dynamic elements of a research output and support claim of use with other tools. For example, if integration with content in other systems is an objective of the digital output, this information allows to assess how feasible it is to aggregate content from this output with other sources (see Sahle 2014).

If the dynamic components of the output rely on proprietary software or plugins, as opposed to open-source software, this choice should be justified whether in the editorial documentation, technical overview or the REF submission itself to give panel members enough elements to assess the dynamic components.

Data processing should follow a comprehensive workflow from input validation through analysis to visualisation, with quality control measures implemented at each stage. The output should document this process emphasising rigorous

validation, error handling, and performance monitoring, while providing clear guidelines for result interpretation and quality assessment through defined metrics and benchmarks.

Examples:

<https://observablehq.com/@jmiguelv/language-of-mechanisation>

<https://github.com/kingsdigitallab/refida>

Example of software citation recommendations:

<https://www.software.ac.uk/guide/how-cite-and-describe-software-you-used-your-research-top-ten-tips>

**Sustain-
ability**

If the output is an access or reference resource claiming to support updates or post-publication activities and/or to be accessible and maintained in the long term, does it provide comprehensive information on its long-term sustainability, such as details regarding the hosting institution’s reliability, Service Level Agreements, and maintenance responsibilities?

Are preservation standards explicitly stated, with explanations of their benefits and limitations, and evidence of the host’s Research Software Engineering or technical expertise to ensure reliable, ongoing support?

Sustainable practices like streamlined code, data transfer optimisation, and minimal file sizes serve both environmental goals and enhance the user experience, with faster load times particularly valuable for users on limited bandwidth. For REF submissions, creators are expected to address sustainability comprehensively, considering aspects like security, backup processes, and the long-term value of institutional versus commercial hosting. In the end, these practices contribute to an eco-friendlier digital presence while ensuring access to and, when relevant, preservation of a resilient, user-friendly resource.

Example of footer with link to SLA provider:

<http://www.historicalpageants.ac.uk/>

Resources:

<https://sustainablewebdesign.org/>

<https://www.websitecarbon.com/>

<https://www.wholegraindigital.com/blog/website-energy-efficiency/>

<https://w3c.github.io/sustyweb/>

**Usage and
analytics**

Are reports or data on usage provided with the REF submission?

Information on data usage provided with contextual narrative for a submission of a digital output are an indicator of the attention paid to monitor use;⁷ they are useful to demonstrate how the output is relevant for its intended (or additional pool of) users and to assess its reach when relevant (especially for impact case studies). However, “levels of usage should not be viewed as a key indicator of the

⁷ For more information on monitoring methods, see Smithies and Ciula 2020.

scholarly value, or even impact, of a resource” (AHRC and ICT Strategy project, 2006: 26).

Usage reports (where relevant or possible), on the other hand, can be useful to indicate high engagement with the output, wide-spread recognition in the scholarly or other relevant communities and international audience (Smithies 2012).

CONTACTS

For projects that are not hosted and maintained by King’s Digital Lab, the following institutions or laboratories might be able to help make a digital output eligible as a 3 or 4* REF submission, in line with the guidance provided in this document (especially important for overseas engineering teams). Please note that they might need a considerable notice period to take on the work.*

- DHI, University of Sheffield: <https://www.dhi.ac.uk/>
- Digital Humanities Lab, University of Exeter: <https://www.exeter.ac.uk/research/digitalhumanities/digital-lab/>
- Dreaming Spires: <https://dreamingspires.dev/>

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CASRAI *CRedit* (Contributor Roles Taxonomy): <https://www.casrai.org/credit.html>

DANS *File formats*: <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/depositing-data-manual/>
Hagstrom, Stephanie (3 September 2014) “The FAIR Data Principles.” FORCE11: <https://force11.org/info/the-fair-data-principles/>

King’s College London Library Services *Research Data Management*: <https://www.kcl.ac.uk/library/researchsupport/research-data-management/index>

MLA (February 2012) *Guidelines for Evaluating Work in Digital Humanities and Digital: Media* <https://www.mla.org/About-Us/Governance/Committees/Committee-Listings/Professional-Issues/Committee-on-Information-Technology/Guidelines-for-Evaluating-Work-in-Digital-Humanities-and-Digital-Media>

MLA (February 2013) *Guidelines for Authors of Digital Resources*: <https://www.mla.org/About-Us/Governance/Committees/Committee-Listings/Professional-Issues/Committee-on-Information-Technology/Guidelines-for-Authors-of-Digital-Resources>

Open Knowledge Foundation, Open Definition project *Conformant Licences*:
<http://opendefinition.org/licenses/>

Purdue University The Online Writing Lab (OWL). *MLA Works Cited: Electronic Sources*:
https://owl.purdue.edu/owl/research_and_citation/mla_style/mla_formatting_and_style_guide/mla_works_cited_electronic_sources.html

REF (June 2023) REF 2028: *Initial decisions and issues for further consultation*:
<https://repository.jisc.ac.uk/9148/1/research-excellence-framework-2028-initial-decisions-report.pdf>

REF (July 2020) *Guidance on submissions to REF 2021*: [ref-2019_01-guidance-on-submissions.pdf](#)

REF (January 2021) *Panel criteria and working methods*: [ref-2019_02-panel-criteria-and-working-methods.pdf](#)

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Sahle, Patrick (June 2014) *Criteria for Reviewing Scholarly Digital Editions, version 1.1*. In collaboration with Georg Vogeler and the members of the IDE. English version 1.1:
<https://www.i-d-e.de/publikationen/weitereschriften/criteria-version-1-1/>

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Smithies, James and Ciula, Arianna (2020) Humans in the Loop. In: K. Schuster and S. Dunn, *Routledge International Handbook of Research Methods in Digital Humanities*, London: Routledge.

Tanner, Simon (2 February 2015) “3 reasons why REF2014 was good for digital humanities scholars” When the Data hits the Fan! The blog of Simon Tanner (@SimonTanner)

UK Government Digital Services (20 May 2019) *Sample accessibility statement (for a fictional public sector website)*:
<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/sample-accessibility-statement/sample-accessibility-statement-for-a-fictional-public-sector-website>

UK Home Office *Accessibility posters*:
https://github.com/UKHomeOffice/posters/blob/master/accessibility/dos-donts/posters_en-UK/accessibility-posters-set.pdf

W3C (21 September 2023) *Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.1*:
<https://www.w3.org/TR/WCAG21/>